

D6.11 Demo videos second version

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Executive summary

This deliverable presents an updated version of a set of video demos of the features of the intelligent services integrated in the VitiGEOSS platform. The platform offers integrated services for sub-seasonal and seasonal predictions, crop management, disease warning, business operations and sustainability monitoring. Additionally, this deliverable presents a novel service on drone monitoring for analysing crop status.

These videos aim to showcase and provide guidance to wine makers as they navigate the various intelligent services integrated into the VitiGEOSS solution. The development of these videos adheres to a standardized design format, crafted to maintain uniformity across the entire series. The purpose is to furnish winemakers with clear, concise, and easily understandable demonstrations, facilitating their seamless comprehension and utilization of the diverse smart services available on the VitiGEOSS Platform.

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List of abbreviations

<i>EU</i>	<i>European Union</i>
<i>EO</i>	<i>Earth Observation</i>
<i>WP</i>	<i>Work Package</i>
<i>VCI</i>	<i>Visual Corporative Image</i>

Introduction

VitiGEOSS, a 3,5-year EU-project, is dedicated to advancing the utilization of European open Earth Observation (EO) services. Its primary goal is to create an innovative vineyard management tool by seamlessly integrating EO data and in-field sensors. This integration is designed to enhance the resolution and reliability of satellite information specifically tailored for application in the viticulture sector.

Beyond the immediate technological objectives, the project also addresses broader challenges facing the global food and wine industry. In response to the need for sustainable intensification of production, climate change mitigation, reduction of negative environmental impacts, and the promotion of local economic growth, VitiGEOSS seeks to provide strategic solutions.

Within the project framework, Eurecat is the partner in charge of SubTask 6.2.3, specifically focused on the development of a demo videos. This subtask is strategically aligned with the overarching project goals, aiming to produce a comprehensive video guide. The purpose of this guide is to navigate users through the diverse smart services developed within Work Package 2 (WP2) and the portal deployed by Work Package 3 (WP3).

Moreover, the videos serve as a crucial role in providing the necessary context for users to comprehend the challenges, motivations, and ultimate outcomes of the VitiGEOSS project.

By offering a holistic view, this demo video contributes to the project's broader objective of fostering understanding and engagement among stakeholders involved in the viticulture sector. At M24, Eurecat with the help of partners agreed to not only produce one video showing the whole platform, but a total of five demo videos, one for each of the five intelligent services integrated in the platform (weather & climate forecasts, phenology monitoring, crop status, disease management and business & sustainability). The structure, contents, and elements of the first version of these demo videos developed are included in D6.6. *Demo Videos*.

At M40, a second version of the videos has been produced, showing the new features being integrated into the platform and highlighting the goal and potential use of each of the services. In this series of videos, a sixth video on the drone monitoring service developed as part of the phenology service has been produced as an additional video material.

In this update, the design of the videos has been changed with the inclusion of a voice over guiding the images being shown on the screen and the creation of a frame to increase consistency amongst the different videos.

This deliverable includes the script prepared, design elements considered for deploying the VitiGEOSS project brand and access to the video uploaded to the project's YouTube channel.

Methodology used for the development of demo videos

The production of the second version of the demo videos for the VitiGEOSS project followed several steps, ensuring a cohesive and effective presentation of the innovative services integrated into the platform. The key steps involved in this process are as follows:

1. Agreement on video format (May 2023, during the General Assembly):

An initial crucial step involved reaching a consensus with project partners on the video format. The collaborative decision was made to utilize a voice-over narration, complemented by screenshots of the VitiGEOSS platform. Additionally, other relevant images were incorporated to enhance and visually support the explanation of each service.

2. Script definition in one-on-one meetings (September - October 2023):

To tailor the content to the intricacies of each Intelligent Service, individualized one-on-one meetings were organized with partners responsible for these services (EUT, LINKS, ELEAF). The leaders of the Intelligent Services prepared an initial version of the script, which was then refined collaboratively through feedback and input from Eurecat.

3. Development of design elements (November 2023):

Eurecat took the lead in developing design elements that maintained a consistent appearance across all videos. This step helps in ensuring uniformity and reinforcing the project's cohesive visual identity.

4. Recording voice over and gathering visual materials (November - December 2023):

Once the script was finalized, the next phase involved recording the voice-over. Simultaneously, project partners focused on gathering all visual materials necessary for illustrating the functionalities of each service. This inclusive approach ensured that both the audio and visual components were curated to effectively communicate the features of the VitiGEOSS platform.

5. Integration of elements for video production (December 2023):

In the final stage, all components - voice-over narration, platform recordings, and design elements - were seamlessly integrated. This process ensured that each video adhered to the established format and maintained a unified look and feel.

6. Public release (December 2023 - January 2024):

The resulting videos were uploaded to the project YouTube account. Subtitles in English were added to support the comprehension of the voice over. During January 2024, the videos will be disseminated through VitiGEOSS project channels (website and social media), and will be used in upcoming events.

Structure and design elements

For the development of the VitiGEOSS services demo videos, a common format was defined regarding the structure and design elements used. Several elements developed for the first series of demo videos (in M24) were reused, such as an animation of the logo of the project to be used as the entry slide of all videos and a final slide animated with VitiGEOSS key information was produced, including: a) VitiGEOSS website, b) VitiGEOSS social media accounts, c) partners logos, d) reference to EU funding.

Figure 1: Entry and ending animated slides used in all demo videos

In the creation of the second batch of demo videos, a decision was made to incorporate a frame that followed the project's accent purple colour with VitiGEOSS logo. This design choice aimed to establish a visual cohesion throughout the videos, seamlessly integrating diverse visual elements originating from various sources. By adhering to a consistent colour scheme, the videos not only conveyed a professional and unified appearance but also reinforced the project's brand identity.

Figure 2: Screenshot of a video where the purple frame can be appreciated

Recognizing the influence of auditory elements in enhancing the overall viewer experience, music is employed to infuse rhythm and dynamism, and accompanies the voice over. The soundtrack selected for the videos has been selected from YouTube Music Studio, ensuring compliance with copyright regulations.

The voice over was complemented with written subtitles to support comprehension.

Demo videos developed

Eurecat, in collaboration with BSC, ELEAF, and LINKS, has collaboratively developed a series of six demo videos, each dedicated to showcasing informative services integrated into the VitiGEOSS platform. These services represent a significant advancement as they enhance existing solutions by harmonizing satellite imagery with in-field sensors. The overarching objective is to optimize vineyard management practices and elevate agricultural business operations on economic, environmental, and local levels.

The purpose of these demo videos is to:

- Serve as user-friendly guides, systematically leading end-users through the functionalities of each service.
- Provide comprehensive training on the services' usage.
- Ensure that stakeholders can fully leverage the capabilities of the VitiGEOSS platform, fostering proficiency and maximizing the benefits derived from the integrated technologies.

On the other hand, the demo videos play a pivotal role in the dissemination strategy of the VitiGEOSS project. By effectively communicating the features and advantages of the platform, the videos aim to raise awareness among wine makers, engaging them in the project's exploitation and commercialisation strategy. This not only enhances the understanding of the VitiGEOSS initiative but also encourages broader participation and collaboration within the viticulture community.

In essence, the demo videos act as a bridge, connecting the technical intricacies of the VitiGEOSS platform with the end-users, contributing to the project's overall success and impact within the agricultural landscape. In that sense, these series of videos have been envisioned to use more plain language, so it can be easily understood by all kind of wine makers, and focused less on the technical side (background models and technology used) but more on explaining the potential use of each service and showcasing it.

1. Demo video #1: Weather & Climate

This service relies on advanced techniques to apply sub-seasonal (for the next weeks, up to 1 month) to seasonal climate forecasts (for the next months) in combination with short term weather forecasts (up to 10 days) to help farmers prepare in advance for unusual climate conditions and extreme events that can damage the crop.

1.1 Script

- Weather & Climate forecasts can help in vineyard management by anticipating the expected conditions, such as the temperature and precipitation.
- Climate forecasts are probabilistic, which means that rather than providing an exact value for temperature and other conditions, they express the probability of these conditions falling within the normal, below normal, or above normal categories, compared to what was observed in the past.
- In the VitiGEOSS platform, weather & climate forecasts can be found in the 'Analyse' menu at the top.
- This service provides from short-term weather forecasts, giving information on the conditions expected in the next days.

- To Sub-seasonal forecasts for the next four weeks.
- And seasonal climate forecasts covering the next three months.
- Whenever extreme conditions are predicted, they are shown as additional bars in the graphs.
- Predictions with low skill are shown as "uncertain", meaning the climatology can be used for decision making in these cases. "Uncertain" values vary on place and time, as well as model updates.
- This service can support monitoring grape quality, organising the harvest or preventing the damage of the crop, to other tasks related to vineyard management.

1.2 Demo video produced

The demo video on the weather & climate forecast services can be found here: <https://youtu.be/Xj9tDXfLqGA>

Figure 3: Screenshots of the demo video on the weather & climate forecast service

2. Demo video #2: Phenological monitoring

The phenological monitoring service integrated in the VitiGEOSS platform is an automated system used to predict and monitor the whole phenological annual cycle through the synergic use of phenological models, satellite and in-field observations, allowing users to better plan and organise the whole vineyard management and optimise resources.

2.1 Script

- VITIGE OSS phenology is a specialized service to monitor and forecast vineyard phenology, according to the Baggiolini scale standard.
- We provide farmers with in-depth insights into grapevine phenology, facilitating meticulous harvest planning, risk mitigation, and enhanced in-field activity management.
- In the VITIGE OSS platform, by selecting a field, the 'Phenology' section shows the outcomes of the phenology service. The service is able to work with diverse data sources to grant the applicability to every field.
- We developed 4 different models grouped in two subsets.
- The detection models track the status of vineyard phenology. It exploits Satellites for Deep EO3, and weather station data for Deep Weather Obs. This service enables daily monitoring of vineyard growth status.
- On the other hand, the forecasting models predict the upcoming phenology phases, projecting developments up to four weeks in advance.
- We offer two forecasting models: the process-based Mechanistic model, and the Deep Weather forecast model, both of which work with in-field weather station and climate predictions data. This valuable tool allows for optimized planning of infield activities.
- Recognizing the unique nature of each vineyard, we leverage historical phenology data to calibrate VITIGE OSS models and ensure the provision of reliable dates to winegrowers.
- The achieved phenology date inserted in the form will serve to improve the results for following vegetation season.
- In section Analyse > Phenology, you can compare the outcome of the models across various fields in the vineyard.
- This monitoring and forecasting service empowers winegrowers to make informed decisions in an increasingly complex climate.

2.2 Demo video produced

The demo video on the phenological monitoring service can be found here: <https://youtu.be/xwst7xdb9nY>

Figure 4: Screenshots of the phenological monitoring demo video

3. Demo video #3: Crop status

This service uses satellite imagery to monitor key indicators describing vegetation health status, crop productivity, crop water consumption and crop nitrogen content to optimise irrigation, sampling or selective harvesting, leading to better grape quality and production.

3.1 Script

- The Crop Status service integrated into the VitiGE OSS platform allows to monitor key indicators during the growth season to assess the crop health, productivity, water use and nitrogen content.
- By clicking on the green button, you can select the parameter to visualise. For this demo video we will choose *Evapotranspiration* as an example.
- Let's say it is dry currently and you are not expecting rain, you would like to check what fields experience most impact from this. This will help you make choices with irrigation application.
- The green, yellow, and red colours showing help you compare the fields for the week selected.

- Select a red field to look at it in more detail, this red field shows a relatively low evapotranspiration compared to the others on the farm.
- All data parameters are visualized in a graph. When clicking on a parameter, it becomes the only one visible. You can select the set of parameters you are interested in viewing.
- When looking at the field view you can compare the evapotranspiration with other parameters, for example NDVI and biomass production. This gives you an idea if the low evapotranspiration level is influencing crop growth.
- By scrolling down, you can find the spatial overview maps for this field per week per parameter. If you click on a map, it pops up in a separate screen.
- The maps can help you indicate spatial difference, as there might be a part of the field that is showing different outcomes.
- Here, the statistics tab can help you to quickly see if these levels are showing on different fields too, requiring some further investigating.
- By going through the Crop Status service, the user can quickly zoom in to a specific indicator, compare among fields and support wine producers' decision making.

3.2 Demo video produced

The demo video on the crop status service can be found here: <https://youtu.be/mNXIsJlcj18>

Figure 5: Screenshots of the crop status service demo video

4. Demo video #4: Disease management

The disease management service allows to forecast the disease evolution, considering the meteorological conditions and crop status to optimise the number of treatments and resources used to assure its effectivity.

4.1 Script

- To access the disease forecasting and management service, users need to select the desired vineyard plot and access to the 'Disease Management' tab in the pop-up window.
- This service, integrated in the VitiGEOSS platform, forecasts the disease evolution, and helps optimize the number of treatments and resources used.
- Here, short-term predictions for the next three days for two specific diseases, the downy mildew and the powdery mildew can be found.
- The information cards indicate the date for which the prediction is made and the anticipated risk for that date. If a disease risk is detected, the tool proposes the recommended treatment and fungicide dosage.
- At the bottom, there is also a history of predictions going back 13 days.
- The information cards indicate the risk level through colour coding, depending on whether a low, shown in green, medium, in yellow, or high risk, indicated in red is detected.
- Additionally, this service provides medium-term forecasts, for the next three weeks, and long-term predictions, for the next three months. This allows the vineyard owner to anticipate to potential threats.
- Finally, in the analysis menu, users can find the disease alert system, where thresholds can be set for each plot.
- With this tool, the vineyard owner can set a notification to be sent by email when a potential risk for downy or powdery mildew is detected, in the short, medium, and long term.

4.2 Demo video produced

The demo video on the disease management service can be found here:
<https://youtu.be/AqZcbKhFYf8>

Figure 6: Screenshots of the disease management service demo video

5. Demo video #5: Business & Sustainability manager

This service consists of a resource optimiser and planner service that allows better timing of field operations and better planning of resources needed, thus reducing the use of raw materials, and promoting more sustainable winegrowing.

5.1 Script

- Starting from the home page you can access the “Business & Sustainability” smart service in the drop-down menu.
- The Business management tool of the VitiGE OSS platform allows to optimize task execution schedules, minimizing the time needed to finish them, their economic cost and the environmental impact.
- This tool allows the user to define a set of tasks and work teams with specific properties and capacities. All the elements of the scenario can be tailored to the users’ needs.
- When the scenario has been defined, artificial intelligence algorithms find the optimal schedule and task assignment.
- A calendar-based visualization will show the solution of the optimization process, indicating the start and duration of the task and the associated work team.

- The interface also indicates the resulting economic and environmental cost of the solution.
- To keep track of different campaigns or scenarios, the platform allows to download the current configuration file, so it can be revisited anytime.
- On the other hand, you can access the sustainability tool by going back to the map visualization menu and clicking on the "sustainability" tab of a selected parcel.
- Here you can see a list of some indicators about productivity, usage of resources, business management and environmental impact from that parcel.
- These indicators allow us to monitor the productivity and environmental impact of the fields and compare the results with data from previous years.

5.2 Demo video produced

The demo video on the business & sustainability manager service can be found here: <https://youtu.be/YLV0S4ESHbw>

Figure 7: Screenshots of the business & sustainability manager demo video

6. Demo video #6: Drone monitoring

This service consists of the use of drones for monitoring vineyards' condition. The post-processing of drone images can help wine growers to gain a clear picture on the progress on vegetation density and the health status of the vines.

6.1 Script

- The VitiGEOSS drone-based vineyard analysis service allows wine producers to gain insight into vines' health status. This service can complement satellite imagery with more close-up detailed images that allow to discern between vine rows and ground vegetation.
- This service generates aerial images of the fields, highlighting the areas suffering from diseases and those with more vegetation density.
- As a first step, a drone survey needs to capture a high-resolution aerial view of a vineyard parcel.
- After this, VitiGEOSS artificial intelligence model detects individual vine rows, creating a "vine row mask".
- Finally, vegetation indexes identify areas of increased plant stress over the vine rows, excluding ground vegetation.
- With the vNDVI vegetation index, we measure the health of the vine canopy.
- Vines marked as green are healthy, whereas yellow or red ones indicate potential dryness or disease.
- On the other hand, if we use the vNDVI index to analyse the inter-row space, we can detect the concentration of groundcover vegetation.
- Another index, called Vineyard Density Index (VDI), is used to measure the canopy coverage density and vigor over the vineyard.
- The blue colour indicates regions where the vine population is abundant, while yellow highlights zones in which vines are not as vigorous.
- The use of this service can provide wine producers with accurate information into vineyard's condition through vegetation indexes and make well-informed decisions confidently.

6.2 Demo video produced

The demo video on the drone monitoring service can be found here: <https://youtu.be/V-FGyrAoytQ>

Figure 8: Screenshots of the drone service demo

Conclusions

Within SubTask 6.2.3 several informative and engaging demo videos were developed. These videos, a key component of the project's outreach and education strategy, are intricately designed to provide users with a comprehensive guide through the diverse smart services encapsulated WP2 and WP3, and support the project's exploitation strategy.

At M40 six new videos are available, encompassing a spectrum from weather and climate forecasts to business and sustainability tools for the wine sector. As the project progressed, a second iteration of the demo videos allow to showcase the evolving features of the platform. A noteworthy addition to this series is a sixth video specifically addressing the drone monitoring service.

This update also signifies a refinement in the design approach, introducing a voice-over narrative to guide viewers through the on-screen content and incorporating a consistent frame to enhance visual coherence across all videos. Subtitles were added to support viewers comprehension of the several services.

Next steps in this topic include the dissemination of the novel demo videos through VitiGEOSS website and social media, as well as use them during one-on-one meetings with potential clients of the platform being fostered within WP5.